

Soft Collaborative Gripper for Dressing Assistance

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Abstract—We present the DressGripper, a collaborative gripper designed for safe interactions in wearing operations. The DressGripper accounts for the two main goals that have to be achieved by a robotic system designed for helping people to get dressed: *i*) to be intrinsically safe and *ii*) to keep firmly the cloth during the dressing operations. The DressGripper addresses these issues by combining a compliant and safe structure with an additional magnetic actuation at the fingertips. This solution allows a soft interaction with the robot and guarantees the grasping tightness. Preliminary experiments show the DressGripper suitability in robotic dressing assistance scenarios.

Index Terms—Grippers and Other End-Effectors; Safety in HRI; Soft Robot Applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Robot-assisted dressing is a tight human-robot collaboration requiring the strict adoption of the principle “safety first”. During dressing, the human and their robotic mate coexist in a very limited space, and can get in contact even unexpectedly. Hence, the robotic end-effectors plays a key role, and soft robotic grippers should be employed [1]. Such end-effectors, indeed, are able to easily deform during interactions, being therefore able to absorb the energy of unexpected collisions, and allowing intrinsically safer interactions than those that can occur with rigid grippers. Here we present DressGripper [2], a tendon-driven underactuated gripper with magnetic actuation, attained by embedding properly located magnetic elements, which can act as additional degrees of actuation (DoAs) operating in specific locations of the gripper. Hence, they can act synergistically with the more global effect provided by classic actuation and transmission components (like motors and tendons), arousing a complementarity enriching of the device’s capabilities.

A. Related works

Grasping and manipulating garments is a great challenge in robotics. Garments, indeed, are millimetric-thick objects with extremely high deformability. However, the vast majority of grippers used in garment manipulation are not specifically designed for interaction with fabrics [3]. Moreover, the grippers used in autonomous garment manipulation are not specifically

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Fig. 1: (a) The DressGripper, (b) CAD model showing two possible embodiments

designed to allow safe human-robot interactions. Usually, indeed, garments are manipulated in industrial settings, where reliability, high-speed and accuracy are privileged.

II. THE DRESSGRIPPER

The DressGripper is a 3D-printed underactuated soft-rigid gripper composed of two modular fingers connected to a base, which contains all the electronic components. The DressGripper is specifically designed to exploit a synergy between tendon-driven and magnetic actuations. The fingers are tendon-actuated: the transmission system conveys the force from the motor to the fingers thanks to tendons connecting the motor to the fingers. The fingertips are equipped with magnetic elements that are the source of the magnetic actuation. Tendon-driven actuation allows the flexion/extension of the fingers, while magnetic actuation is in charge of empowering the contact permanence between the fingertips, reflecting on the tightness of the garment grasping.

Each finger of the DressGripper is a kinematic chain composed of two identical modules ending with a fingertip module. In one of the two fingers, such a fingertip module contains an electromagnet. On the other finger, the fingertip can contain two different elements: it can host another electromagnet, or it can house a small ferromagnetic plate (see Fig. 1b). The rationale is that the proper choice depends on the use-case. Electromagnets, indeed, are capable of exerting high grip (magnetic) forces but may have non-negligible power consumption, especially in prolonged use. Although higher forces allow manipulating heavy and thick clothes, high power consumption requires connecting the gripper to the power supply. The fingertip’s embodiment exploiting only one electromagnet, instead, requires less power consumption, hence it is suitable for being used with a battery, and can be mounted also on a passive robotic arm. Grip forces will be usually

Fig. 2: (a) FEM analysis related to magnetic attraction. (b) Setup for the estimate of the force to be applied for grasp breaking.

TABLE I: Fabrics used for characterizing the DressGripper capabilities. In the last two columns, we report the average force required to break the grasp in the EP and EE embodiments. “W” and “T” stand for “weight” and “thickness” of the garment, respectively.

Sample	W [g]	T [mm]	F_{EPE} [N]	F_{EEE} [N]
Trousers 1	6.23	0.62	1.41 ± 0.16	2.19 ± 0.38
Trousers 2	7.80	0.94	1.17 ± 0.13	1.74 ± 0.10
Jeans	7.07	0.72	1.33 ± 0.25	3.12 ± 0.34
Undersh1	5.77	0.70	1.66 ± 0.17	4.60 ± 0.57
Undersh 2	2.81	0.70	2.86 ± 0.16	9.85 ± 0.48
T-Shirt	2.46	0.52	2.66 ± 0.03	7.52 ± 0.68
Shirt 1	2.27	0.26	1.77 ± 0.14	9.21 ± 0.25
Shirt 2	4.50	0.66	1.59 ± 0.17	5.18 ± 0.41
Fleece	3.85	1.10	1.61 ± 0.06	5.69 ± 0.46
Sweater	3.92	1.06	1.48 ± 0.14	4.34 ± 0.13

lower than those generated by two electromagnets, hence this configuration is more suitable to thin and light garments. More details on the FEM structural analysis conducted for a proper definition of the fingers’ embodiments are provided in [2], as well as the kinematic analysis for the fingers trajectory.

III. EXPERIMENTS

To have insights on the actual performance of the DressGripper when manipulating fabrics, we selected 10 samples of fabric commonly used for clothes Table I. Trousers are made of stretch cotton, with “Trousers1” more elastic than “Trousers2”. “Jeans” are the less stretchy trousers. “Shirt1” is made of pure cotton, while “Shirt2” is a stretchy material containing elastane, cotton and polyester. “Fleece” is 100% polyester. “Undershirt1” is made of cotton 98%, elastane 2%, with very narrow ribs, while “Undershirt2” is made of cotton 95% and 5% elastane, and has ribs large 2 mm. “T-shirt” is made of cotton 98% and 2% elastane.

Concerning the experimental procedure, experiments were aimed at testing the DressGripper’s ability to resist perturbations while pinch grasping different fabrics. A clip was attached to the fabric, and a dynamometer was attached to that clip. Forces were applied to the fabrics, using a dynamometer fixed to a manual test stand. The test stand was equipped with a linear encoder for displacement measurement. Once the fingers were closed, the fabrics between the fingertips were trapped. Traction was exerted on the fabric until the sample began to slide Fig. 2. The procedure was repeated 10 times, and then forces were averaged. Results are reported in Table I.

Experiments reveal that thickness is not the only parameter that has to be considered to gain insights on the force required to break the grasp. Relevant characteristics are *i)* the fabric slip, *ii)* the pattern of the garment in the vertical direction, *iii)* the fibers’ density. Concerning *i)*, the more man-made fibers are present, the more the fabric is slippery (as it can be noticed also by touching the fabric with hands). Regarding *ii)*, the more irregular the arrangement of full and empty spaces is along the vertical direction (e.g., in the fleece), the more easily the grasp breaks. Concerning *iii)*, the denser the fabric in both the horizontal plane and the vertical direction, the stronger should be the magnetic force to ensure the grasp maintenance. More details on the experimental results can be found in [2].

Moreover, to have insights on the DressGripper capabilities during robot-assisted dressing, we implemented a human-robot cooperative scenario, exploiting the collaborative 7-DoF Sawyer robotic arm. Since we were using a non-passive robot, we exploited the DressGripper equipped with two electromagnets, which proved to resist more than the embodiment consisting in one electromagnet and one ferromagnetic plate. Through kinesthetic teaching, we recorded a trajectory of the robotic arm aimed at helping a human to wear the sleeve of a shirt. For this test, we used a shirt different from the ones used in the previous experiments. The human is supposed to have one of his/her arm almost straight in front of him/her (as in Fig. 1), while the robot grasps the shirt near the neck and gently moves towards the human, successfully fitting the sleeve on the human arm, as shown in the multimedia attachment to the paper.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A specific type of collaborative robotic task where the robot end-effector is expected to come into touch with the human body is robotic dressing assistance. In this work, we presented the DressGripper, a collaborative soft gripper specifically designed for this task. In order to allow the gripper to grasp the garment and to resist the disturbance forces that may reach high values and that could be hardly resisted by only the gripper soft structures, two different embodiments have been proposed: EE, with two electromagnets, and EP, which exploits the presence of one electromagnet and a soft ferromagnetic plate. The EP solution has lower power consumption and may thus be employed with a battery in use-cases involving passive supports, whereas the EE embodiment, allows applying greater gripping pressures for grasp maintenance but has a larger power consumption than the EP embodiment.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. M. Dollar and R. D. Howe, “The highly adaptive sdm hand: Design and performance evaluation,” *The international journal of robotics research*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 585–597, 2010.
- [2] M. Dragusanu, S. Marullo, M. Malvezzi, G. M. Achilli, M. C. Valigi, D. Prattichizzo, and G. Salvietti, “The dressgripper: A collaborative gripper with electromagnetic fingertips for dressing assistance,” *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 7479–7486, 2022.
- [3] J. Borràs, G. Alenyà, and C. Torras, “A grasping-centered analysis for cloth manipulation,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 924–936, 2020.